

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

IMPLEMENTATION OF INTRA-SUBJECT CONNECTIONS DURING TEACHING GEOMETRIC CONCEPTS

Shukurov Rasim Yusif

Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University

Associate Professor of the Department of Technology of Teaching Primary Courses in Mathematics

Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogy

ORCID: 0009-0002-9344-5422

Abstract

This article examines the role of interdisciplinary connections in teaching geometric concepts during the training of primary school teachers at pedagogical universities. It also identifies ways to implement these connections in the course "Basic Geometric Concepts and Propositions."

Keywords: primary school, interdisciplinary connections, geometry, spatial representation, learning

Introduction

The basis for the subsequent stages of students' mathematical education is the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by them in primary school. Therefore, the organization of teaching mathematics in primary school in accordance with modern requirements requires the teacher to have deep knowledge of the essence of mathematical concepts and facts, as well as high pedagogical skills. Every elementary school teacher who will teach mathematics must be familiar with its general ideas, be able to see the connections of these ideas with the educational material being studied, and be able to identify these connections if necessary.

Every primary school teacher should know that the mathematics he teaches during his school years forms the scientific and theoretical basis of the mathematics he teaches in primary school. Therefore, it is extremely important that every subject taught in higher education, especially mathematics, is based on intra-subject connections. In addition to establishing fundamental mathematical concepts such as geometric concepts, elementary school introduces students to the elements of geometry and develops spatial awareness and logical reasoning abilities. All this implies that the mathematical training of primary school teachers should be especially high. Every primary school teacher, in addition to a deep knowledge of the scientific and theoretical aspects of simple geometric concepts, must also know simple spatial figures, their properties, have the skills to describe simple spatial figures on a plane, be able to justify the choice of a particular mathematical solution method and be able to identify relationships between simple spatial figures in the process of solving a problem [1,237].

As is known, in elementary school simple geometric concepts are given to students without a serious logical definition of these concepts, and in most cases - in a ready-made form. Therefore, these concepts must be completely logically understandable to the teacher. In addition, a primary school teacher must be able to use the subject of mathematics taught by him as a tool for educating students, broadening their horizons and increasing interest in mathematics [2,9]. All this requires significant methodological and mathematical prepara-

tion from the teacher. These requirements for mathematical training and professional skills of students studying in the specialty "Primary school teacher" determine the need to teach geometric concepts based on intra-subject connections. A student studying in this specialty must understand that, knowing at the required level the scientific and theoretical basis of each geometric concept that he will teach to schoolchildren, he will be able to find the most effective way to explain this concept. Therefore, every future primary school teacher must take into account that the specific geometric concept that he will teach has a scientific and theoretical basis, and he must be ready to substantiate this concept from a scientific and theoretical point of view in a future lesson. This can only be achieved if students are trained in geometry during the learning process at the level of modern scientific, pedagogical and methodological requirements, including taking into account intra-subject connections [3,5]. The use of spatial relationships when teaching the elements of geometry is very important, especially in the stereometry section. The section of stereometry includes the study of three-dimensional figures and their properties. Using spatial relationships when teaching this section is important to deepen students' spatial awareness and increase their understanding of the subject [4,112].

The use of spatial relationships when teaching the section of stereometry is mainly manifested in the following:

- spatial imagination: visual aids (models, drawings) should be used to help students imagine three-dimensional objects. This helps to understand the shape, volume and other properties of objects.

- analysis and comparison: using spatial relationships, you can compare the properties of different objects (for example, prisms, cylinders, cones). This helps learners understand the similarities and differences between objects.

- solving geometric problems: by applying non-standard approaches to solving problems related to stereometry, more effective solutions can be found. For example, calculating volume, finding surface area, etc.

– interactive teaching methods: the use of interactive methods in lessons allows students to be more actively involved in the learning process. This facilitates the application of non-standard ratios in real life.

– practical tasks: students should be asked to apply the learned theory by offering practical tasks, for example, on making or modeling three-dimensional figures.

Conclusion

Methodically considering the ways of using intra-subject connections when teaching geometric concepts in the process of training pedagogical personnel in the specialty "Primary school teacher", we come to the following conclusions:

– it is extremely important that the teaching of each subject in higher education, especially geometry, is based on intra-subject connections.

– the use of intra-subject connections when teaching geometry develops students' spatial perception, helps them better understand the subject and apply it in practice. This approach also creates conditions for increasing the interest and interactivity of lessons - the use of intra-subject connections when teaching basic

geometric concepts closely contributes to the teaching of other subjects.

- the use of intra-subject connections when teaching geometry increases the level of students' assimilation of the section of stereometry, expands their spatial representations, which leads to an increase in the quality of teaching the subject and the training of teaching staff in general.

References

1. A.M. Ashurov. Basic geometric concepts and proposals (tutorial). Baku, 2021, 248 pages.

2. A.M. Ashurov. Basic geometric concepts and propositions (problems). Teaching materials. Baku, 2022, 245 pages.

3. S.A. Feyziyev, R.Y. Shukurov. Theoretical foundations of the elementary course of mathematics (textbook), Baku, 2010, 568 pages.

4. S.A. Feyziyev, R.Y. Shukurov. Theoretical foundations of the elementary course of mathematics (elements of geometry) (textbook) Part III. Baku "Education" 2004, 132 pages.